

PHYSICOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS, ACCEPTABILITY, AND MARKETABILITY OF GUYASIL (GUYABANO AND BASIL) SALAD DRESSING

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 22

Issue 5

Pages: 607-618

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2084

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12797243

Manuscript Accepted: 06-19-2024

Physicochemical Analysis, Acceptability, and Marketability of Guyasil (Guyabano And Basil) Salad Dressing

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Abstract

This study attempted to determine the Physicochemical Analysis, Acceptability, and Marketability of GuyaSil salad dressing with 55 grams, 65 grams, and 75 grams of Guyabano pulp with 10 grams of Basil leaves. The study utilized the experimental method of research which involved a total of 90 respondents from the group of food experts, food enthusiasts, and food critics who were determined through purposive sampling. The level of acceptability of the GuyaSil Salad Dressing in three different proportions of Guyabano pulp and Basil leaves were evaluated using a Nine-point Hedonic Rating Scale and the level of marketability were evaluated using a Four-point Likert Rating Scale. The results revealed that in a hundred-gram sample, GuyaSil Salad Dressing contains 45 calories, 88.1 grams of moisture, 0.160/100g fat content, 0.738 g ash content, and 0.894 protein content. Likewise, the evaluations on the level of acceptability of the product obtained different ratings which led to significant differences in their evaluations. Meanwhile, the level of marketability was rated High Potential resulting in a significant difference in their assessment. The comments and suggestions offered by the three groups of respondents on the concocted GuyaSil Salad Dressing for the improvement of the product.

Keywords: *acceptability, marketability, physicochemical analysis, salad dressing*

Introduction

In the middle of the COVID-19 pandemic, more people are beginning to pay attention to their health and make dietary changes to strengthen their immune systems. The goal of enabling people to enjoy salads without having to count calories or worry about potential health risks, researchers are looking into the potential nutritional and safety benefits of using natural ingredients like basil and soursop in salad dressings, as well as exploring any potential health advantages associated with these ingredients.

Salad is one of the alternatives on the healthy plate, meal by meal. Half of a meal should be vegetables, quarters should be protein, and fourths should be carbohydrates. Because of this, salad is one of the best options for a healthy plate, yet most salad dressings contain dangerous substances these days. They contain more fat and calories than other foods. This causes your diet to fail.

Soursop, also known as guyabano, is one of the best fruits grown, especially in our nation. Several research claims that Guyabano can treat cancer. According to Tan (2019), a Graviola extract's naturally occurring chemicals inhibited several signaling pathways that regulate PC cells' metabolism, cell cycle, survival, and metastatic abilities.

On the other hand, another ingredient used by the researcher is basil. Basil leaves also have tremendous pharmaceutical benefits, and it is commonly use in rice, meat, stews, and soups. It has historically been used to treat renal issues, as a haemostyptic after childbirth, earaches, irregular menstrual cycles, arthritis, anorexia, colds, and malaria. Positive results against bacterial, fungal, viral, and other infections have been demonstrated with basil. Basil leaves have been used to treat asthma, coughs, the flu, and fevers, bronchitis, influenza, and diarrhea. (Shahrajabian & Sun, 2020).

Dietary use, herbal medication, and the use of basil essential oil all have potential health benefits. Traditional applications include, among others, curing colds, snakebites, and nasal irritation, a frequent cold side effect. In addition to numerous macronutrients like calcium and vitamin K, basil also contains a variety of antioxidants.

Research Questions

This study attempted to determine the Physicochemical Analysis, Acceptability, and Marketability of GUYASIL salad dressing with 55 grams, 65 grams, and 75 grams of Guyabano pulp with 10 grams of Basil leaves, as evaluated by the food experts, food enthusiast, and food critics during the school year 2023-2024 at Marikina Polytechnic College. More specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. How was salad dressing with three different proportions of guyabano pulp and basil leaves prepared?
2. What was the physicochemical analysis of the concocted GuyaSil Salad Dressing in terms of the following aspects:
 - 2.1. calories;
 - 2.2. moisture;
 - 2.3. potential for hydrogen (ph);
 - 2.4. fats;
 - 2.5. ash; and
 - 2.6. protein?

3. What was the level of acceptability of Guyabano pulp in three proportions with Basil leaves Salad Dressing as evaluated by the food experts, food enthusiasts, and food critics in terms of the following criteria:
 - 3.1. appearance;
 - 3.2. aroma;
 - 3.3. color;
 - 3.4. taste; and
 - 3.5. texture?
4. Were there significant differences in the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the level of acceptability of Guyabano pulp in three proportions with Basil leaves Salad Dressing in terms of the above criteria?
5. What was the level of marketability of the Guyabano pulp in three proportions with Basil leaves Salad Dressing as perceived by the three group of respondents in terms of the following aspects:
 - 5.1. supply availability;
 - 5.2. production cost; and
 - 5.3. consumer demand?
6. Were there significant differences in the perception of the three groups of respondents on the level of marketability of Guyabano pulp in three proportions with Basil leaves Salad Dressing in terms of the above-mentioned criteria?
7. What are the comments and suggestions of the three groups of respondents on the concocted GuyaSil Salad to improve the product?

Literature Review

Ribes et al. (2021) state that salad dressings are emulsions of oil and water that have small oil droplets distributed in the aqueous phase. Dressings are commonly used to improve the flavor and appeal of many different foods, and their use has grown recently. Dressings must be physically stable enough to preserve structural integrity for the duration of the shelf life.

According to an article by Hines et al. (2021), basil is nutritious and full of flavor. With its distinctive flavor, fresh basil is a favorite herb among chefs and home cooks. Making pesto is one of my favorite ways to use basil. Fresh basil, pine nuts, garlic, parmesan cheese, and olive oil are combined to make pesto.

Irshad et al. (2023) claimed that the Lamiaceae plant known as *Ocimum basilicum*, or sweet basil is native to regions like Africa, tropical Asia, South America, and Central America. It emits a captivating combination of sweet and spicy fragrance and is often cultivated for both culinary and aromatic purposes. Beyond its role as a flavor enhancer, sweet basil has garnered attention for its potential health benefits. Traditional medicine has employed it to alleviate gastrointestinal issues, menstrual cramps, and kidney function, among others.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized the experimental method of research to achieve its main objectives. Experimental method refers to a research approach employed to cause-and-effect relationships between variables. This technique involves altering independent variables and subsequently observing the impact on dependent variables, as previously discussed. This has been defined by the two authors in various ways.

Participants

The sources of data in this research were from thirty (30) food experts, thirty (30) food enthusiasts, and thirty (30) food critics from Marikina Polytechnic College, Marikina City during the school year 2023-2024.

Instruments

The evaluation questionnaire was administered to determine the Physicochemical Analysis, Acceptability, and Marketability of GuyaSil Salad Dressing with 55 grams, 65 grams and, 75 grams of Guyabano pulp and 10 grams of Basil leaves. The product was evaluated in terms of its sensory attributes in terms of appearance, aroma, color, taste, and texture.

Procedure

The researcher of this study followed procedures to achieve the objectives of this study. First, the researcher produced enough yield of GuyaSil Salad Dressing for the physicochemical analysis and survey. The salad dressing sample for the physicochemical analysis was submitted to the F.A.S.T Laboratories for testing. Second, she obtained a permit from the Research and Development Office to conduct a study in the college. The researcher presented the evaluation questionnaire to the research advisor for approval. The questionnaire had 21 indicators which were related to the target respondent's evaluation about salad dressing. In the questionnaire, a Nine-Point Hedonic Scale and Four-Point Likert Rating Scale were used to determine the respondent's evaluation in each indicator. The researcher asked different field experts to validate the evaluation questionnaire after which, the researcher prepared ninety copies which these

were administered to thirty (30) food experts, thirty (30) food enthusiasts, and thirty (30) food critics from Marikina Polytechnic College.

The questionnaires were personally answered by the three groups of respondents and each evaluation was kept confidential. No individual identities were used and shown as part of the report and interpretation. After gathering the evaluations, the data were tallied, tabulated, and statistically treated for analysis and interpretation.

Ethical Considerations

The study made sure that protecting the respondents' anonymity and privacy is a top priority. Additionally, the proper consent and authorization were considered. Participants in the study did not suffer any material, emotional, or physical harm from the researcher, and any information gathered from them were acknowledged and presented fairly.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings according to the study's research questions.

Prepared Salad Dressing with Different Proportions of Guyabano Pulp with Basil Leaves

Extract Guyabano pulp in amounts of 55 grams, 65 grams, and 75 grams each mixture was combined it with basil leaves and other ingredients using a blender with the process of continue blending until the mixture attained the desired consistency and optimal texture. Each mixture was carefully packaged and labeled using food-grade containers.

Physicochemical Analysis of the Concocted GuyaSil Salad Dressing with Guyabano Pulp and Basil leaves

Table 1. Summary of Physicochemical Analysis of GuyaSil Salad Dressing

Parameter	Unit	Test Method	Result	Remarks
Calories/100g	--	By computation	45	Low
Moisture	g/100g	Vacuum Oven Drying	88.1	High Activity
Potential of Hydrogen (pH)	--	Electrometry	3.66 @ 23.0°C	Standard acid content
Fat	g/100g	Acid Hydrolysis Mojonnier Extraction	0.160	Low
Ash	g/100g	Ignition- Gravimetry	0.738	Low
Protein	g/100g	Kjeldahl	0.894	Within range

The results revealed that in a hundred-gram sample, GuyaSil Salad Dressing contains 45 calories, computed to classify it as a low-calorie food product, suitable for weight loss. With a moisture content of 88.1 grams, the salad dressing is considered to have high water activity. Furthermore, its potential of hydrogen (pH) value of 3.66 @ 23.0°C meets the standard regulations set by the U.S Department of Agriculture (USDA). The fat content of 0.160/100g is relatively low, allowing GuyaSil Salad Dressing to be claimed as "fat-free." Additionally, the ash content, tested using ignition- gravimetry, revealed that the salad dressing contains 0.738 g of ash, which is lower compared to other commercialized salad dressings. Lastly, the protein content at 0.894 implies that the protein content of the product falls within the range set by FNRI-DOST standards.

Level of Acceptability of Guyasil as Salad Dressing in Three Proportions as Evaluated by the Food Experts, Food Enthusiasts, and Food Critics

For 55 Grams Proportion

Table 2. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 55 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing as regards Appearance

The GuyaSil salad dressing...	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. is tempting to eat.	8.43	VA	7.97	VA	8.00	VA
2. has a visually appetizing color.	8.60	EA	8.13	VA	7.80	VA
3. has a shiny and glossy appearance.	8.67	EA	8.33	VA	7.73	VA
4. appearance unmistakably reflects its revitalizing quality.	8.43	VA	8.17	VA	7.47	MA
5. appears to have well blended ingredients.	8.60	EA	7.97	VA	8.17	VA
Overall Weighted Means	8.55	EA	8.11	VA	7.83	VA

As shown in the table, the Food Experts evaluated the acceptability of GuyaSil Salad Dressing with 55 grams proportion of guyabano pulp and 10 grams proportion of Basil Leaves in terms of appearance as Extremely Acceptable evident from its overall weighted mean of 8.55, while the Food Enthusiasts and Food Critics evaluated rated the GuyaSil Salad Dressing as Very Acceptable with an overall weighted mean of 8.11 and 7.83, respectively. These results implies that the GuyaSill Salad dressing with 55 grams proportion of guyabano pulp and 10 grams of Basil leaves is tempting to eat, shows appetizing color, has shiny and glossy appearance, has revitalizing quality, and has well-blended ingredients.

Table 3. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 55 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing as regards Aroma

The GuyaSil salad dressing...	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. smells really nice.	8.70	EA	7.90	VA	7.73	VA
2. has an appetizing aroma.	8.47	VA	7.80	VA	8.03	VA
3. has no herbaceous, leafy aroma.	8.40	VA	7.97	VA	7.40	MA
4. has delicate sweet aroma.	8.07	VA	7.57	VA	7.23	MA
5. has delicate sour aroma.	7.87	VA	7.87	VA	7.50	VA
Overall Weighted Means	8.30	VA	7.82	VA	7.58	VA

It can be gleaned from the table 12 that the three groups of respondents perceived and accepted the GuyaSil Salad Dressing in 55 grams proportion in terms of its aroma Very Acceptable, evident from the overall weighted mean of 8.30, 7.82, and 7.58, respectively. The results implies that the aroma of the product is a big factor on the salad dressings overall appeal to its target market. All the positive ratings across all indicators shows that the product is well-accepted by the three groups of respondents.

Table 4. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 55 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing as regards Color

The GuyaSil salad dressing...	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. has an even distribution of color.	8.80	EA	8.23	VA	8.20	VA
2. has appetizing and attractive color.	8.53	EA	7.93	VA	7.97	VA
3. has herbaceous green color.	8.83	EA	8.30	VA	7.70	VA
4. has a distinctive green shade color.	8.70	EA	8.30	VA	8.10	VA
5. has a vibrant, appealing color.	8.47	VA	7.93	VA	7.87	VA
Overall Weighted Means	8.67	EA	8.14	VA	7.97	VA

As exhibited in the table, the Food Experts evaluated the acceptability level of the GuyaSil Salad Dressing with 55 grams proportions as Extremely Acceptable with an overall weighted mean of 8.67, while Food Enthusiasts, and Food Critics evaluated the salad dressing as Very Acceptable with an overall weighted mean of 8.14, and 7.97, respectively. These facts indicates that the product is true to claim that is has an even distribution of colors, has an appetizing and attractive color, shows herbaceous color, has a distinctive green color, and has a vibrant appealing color.

Table 5. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 55 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing as regards Taste

The GuyaSil salad dressing...	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. has a harmonious combination of sweet, sour, and savory flavors.	8.33	VA	7.67	VA	8.27	VA
2. has a slightly herbaceous taste.	8.37	VA	7.87	VA	7.87	VA
3. has a delightful and satisfying taste.	8.47	VA	7.73	VA	8.27	VA
4. ingredients harmonize perfectly, creating a well-balanced and flavorful taste	8.53	EA	7.63	VA	8.13	VA
5. has a palatable taste.	8.67	EA	7.43	MA	8.40	VA
Overall Weighted Means	8.47	VA	7.67	VA	8.19	VA

As displayed in the table, the GuyaSil Salad Dressing with 55 grams proportion was rated as Very Acceptable with an overall weighted mean of 8.47, 7.67, and 8.19 by the three groups of respondents, respectively, in terms of taste. All these finding signifies that the taste of the GuyaSil Salad Dressing satisfies all the groups of respondents and indicates that in terms of taste, the product is in highly acceptable.

The table 6 revealed that the group of Food Experts evaluated the GuyaSil Salad Dressing with 55 grams proportion in terms of its texture as Extremely Acceptable with an overall weighted mean of 8.61, while the group of Food Enthusiasts, and Food Critics rated it as Very Acceptable with an overall weighted mean of 8.07, and 8.14, respectively. The data show that the GuyaSil Salad Dressing in 55 grams proportions is commendable for the three groups of respondents as regards texture. These results suggests that texture is one of the best assets of the product.

Table 6. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 55 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing as regards Texture

The GuyaSil salad dressing...	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. has a smooth texture.	8.80	EA	8.40	VA	8.30	VA
2. has dense and substantial texture.	8.60	EA	8.10	VA	8.07	VA
3. has no residue texture.	8.60	EA	7.90	VA	7.83	VA
4. has a rich and indulgent texture	8.57	EA	8.00	VA	8.20	VA
5. has pleasurable and satisfying texture	8.47	VA	7.97	VA	8.30	VA
Overall Weighted Means	8.61	EA	8.07	VA	8.14	VA

For 65 Grams Proportion

Table 7. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 65 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing as regards Appearance

The GuyaSil salad dressing...	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. is tempting to eat.	6.33	SA	6.43	SA	6.80	MA
2. has a visually appetizing color.	6.30	SA	6.47	SA	6.73	MA
3. has a shiny and glossy appearance.	6.90	MA	6.20	SA	6.37	SA
4. appearance unmistakably reflects its revitalizing quality.	6.13	SA	6.20	SA	6.40	SA
5. appears to have well blended ingredients.	6.67	MA	6.37	SA	7.37	MA
Overall Weighted Means	6.47	SA	6.33	SA	6.73	MA

As shown in the table, Food Experts and Food Enthusiasts evaluated the GuyaSil Salad Dressing in 65 grams proportion in terms of appearance as Slightly Acceptable, evident from its overall weighted mean of 6.47, and 6.33, respectively. Moreover, the group of Food critics evaluated the products as Moderately Acceptable with its overall weighted mean of 6.73. Granted that, several improvements can still be made to reach the highest form of acceptability from its target market.

Table 8. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 65 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing as regards Aroma

The GuyaSil salad dressing...	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. smells really nice.	7.43	MA	6.37	SA	7.10	MA
2. has an appetizing aroma.	6.87	MA	6.03	SA	7.63	VA
3. has no herbaceous, leafy aroma.	7.17	MA	6.50	MA	7.00	MA
4. has delicate sweet aroma.	7.03	MA	5.93	SA	6.77	MA
5. has delicate sour aroma.	7.23	MA	6.57	MA	6.43	SA
Overall Weighted Means	7.15	MA	6.28	SA	6.99	MA

It can be gleaned from the table that with an overall weighted mean of 7.15, Food Experts evaluated the Guyabano pulp in 65 grams proportion with Basil leaves Salad Dressing in terms of aroma as Moderately Acceptable, while the Food critics obtained overall weighted mean on 6.99, while the group of Food Enthusiasts rated the product as Slightly Acceptable with its overall weighted mean of 6.28. This implies that the product releases a nice, appetizing, and herbaceous aroma.

Table 9. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 65 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing as regards Color

The GuyaSil salad dressing...	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. has an even distribution of color.	7.37	MA	6.50	MA	7.40	MA
2. has appetizing and attractive color.	7.40	MA	5.73	SA	9.67	EA
3. has herbaceous green color.	7.27	MA	6.07	SA	7.27	MA
4. has a distinctive green shade color.	7.30	MA	6.53	MA	7.37	MA
5. has a vibrant, appealing color.	7.30	MA	6.40	SA	7.37	MA
Overall Weighted Means	7.33	MA	6.25	SA	7.81	VA

The table revealed that the group of Food Experts evaluated the GuyaSil Salad Dressing as Moderately Acceptable with its overall weighted mean of 7.33. Meanwhile, Food Enthusiasts rated the products as Slightly Acceptable, evidently shown from its overall weighted mean of 6.25. Lastly, Food critics gave an evaluation of Very Acceptable with its overall weighted mean of 7.81. The product

shows an even distribution of color, its appetizing and attractive color is significant for the product's market success.

Table 10. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 65 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing as regards Taste

The GuyaSil salad dressing...	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	WM	VI	WM
1. has a harmonious combination of sweet, sour, and savory flavors.	7.33	MA	6.90	7.33	MA	6.90
2. has a slightly herbaceous taste.	7.03	MA	6.17	7.03	MA	6.17
3. has a delightful and satisfying taste.	7.27	MA	6.10	7.27	MA	6.10
4. ingredients harmonize perfectly, creating a well-balanced and flavorful taste	6.53	MA	6.47	6.53	MA	6.47
5. has a palatable taste.	6.97	MA	6.13	6.97	MA	6.13
Overall Weighted Means	7.03	MA	6.35	7.03	MA	6.35

As shown from the table, indicators 1 to 5 was evaluated as Moderately Acceptable by both Food Experts and Food Critics. Additionally, Food Enthusiasts rate indicator 1 as Moderately Acceptable, and indicators 2 to 5 as Slightly Acceptable. With all things considered, the products nature of having harmonious combination of sweet, sour, and savory flavor is acceptable and satisfying for the respondents.

Table 11. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 65 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing as regards Texture

The GuyaSil salad dressing...	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. has a smooth texture.	6.60	MA	5.97	SA	7.37	MA
2. has dense and substantial texture.	6.57	MA	5.53	SA	7.00	MA
3. has no residue texture.	6.77	MA	6.33	SA	6.63	MA
4. has a rich and indulgent texture	6.53	MA	5.70	SA	6.90	MA
5. has pleasurable and satisfying texture	6.97	MA	6.50	MA	7.10	MA
Overall Weighted Means	6.69	MA	6.01	SA	7.00	MA

As displayed from the table, both Food Experts and Food Critics rated the GuyaSil Salad Dressing with 65 grams proportion as Moderately Acceptable in terms of texture with overall weighted mean of 6.69, and 7.00, respectively. Meanwhile, Food Enthusiasts rated the product Slightly Acceptable with overall weighted mean of 6.01.

For 75 Grams Proportion

Table 12. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 75 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing as regards Appearance

The GuyaSil salad dressing...	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. is tempting to eat.	5.87	SA	5.97	SA	6.20	SA
2. has a visually appetizing color.	6.67	MA	5.90	SA	6.70	MA
3. has a shiny and glossy appearance.	5.47	FA	5.60	SA	6.67	MA
4. appearance unmistakably reflects its revitalizing quality.	6.20	SA	5.80	SA	6.63	MA
5. appears to have well blended ingredients.	5.80	SA	6.17	SA	7.27	MA
Overall Weighted Means	6.00	SA	5.89	SA	6.69	MA

As presented in the table 13, the GuyaSil Salad Dressing with 75 grams proportion is evaluated by Food Experts and Food Enthusiasts as Slightly Acceptable with an overall weighted mean of 6.00 and 5.89, respectively, and Moderately Acceptable by the Food Critics with the overall weighted mean of 6.69. It shows that the view of the respondents on the appearance of the product is good and is acceptable.

Table 13. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 75 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing as regards Aroma

The GuyaSil salad dressing...	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. smells really nice.	6.93	MA	6.07	SA	6.53	MA
2. has an appetizing aroma.	7.20	MA	5.73	SA	7.13	MA

3. has no herbaceous, leafy aroma.	6.60	MA	5.40	FA	6.70	MA
4. has delicate sweet aroma.	6.70	MA	5.93	SA	6.40	SA
5. has delicate sour aroma.	6.77	MA	6.57	MA	6.67	MA
Overall Weighted Means	6.84	MA	5.94	SA	6.69	MA

Table 14. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 75 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing as regards Color

	The GuyaSil salad dressing...					
	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. has an even distribution of color.	7.43	MA	6.17	SA	7.17	MA
2. has appetizing and attractive color.	7.10	MA	5.90	SA	7.37	MA
3. has herbaceous green color.	7.17	MA	5.90	SA	7.00	MA
4. has a distinctive green shade color.	7.47	MA	6.20	SA	7.07	MA
5. has a vibrant, appealing color.	7.23	MA	6.00	SA	7.43	MA
Overall Weighted Means	7.28	MA	6.03	SA	7.21	MA

As gleaned from the table, Indicators 1 to 5 are evaluated by Food Experts and Food Critics as Moderately Acceptable. In the similar note, Food Enthusiasts rated all five indicators as Slightly Acceptable. This suggests that the product has a favorable color that can be considered as a strong point once it reached the public.

Table 15. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 75 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing as regards Taste

	The GuyaSil salad dressing...					
	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. has a harmonious combination of sweet, sour, and savory flavors.	7.00	MA	6.00	SA	7.73	VA
2. has a slightly herbaceous taste.	6.93	MA	5.63	SA	6.97	MA
3. has a delightful and satisfying taste.	6.83	MA	5.13	FA	6.87	MA
4. ingredients harmonize perfectly, creating a well-balanced and flavorful taste	6.70	MA	6.03	SA	7.00	MA
5. has a palatable taste.	6.70	MA	5.50	SA	7.13	MA
Overall Weighted Means	6.83	MA	5.66	SA	7.14	MA

The table displayed that the acceptability level of Food Experts and Food Critics on the GuyaSil Salad Dressing with 75 grams proportion in terms of Taste is at Moderate Acceptance given from its overall weighted mean of 6.83 and 7.14, while Slightly Acceptable for Food Enthusiasts with its overall weighted mean of 5.66. This implies that the product has a good taste and is well perceived by the three groups of respondents.

Table 16. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 75 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing as regards Texture

	The GuyaSil salad dressing...					
	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. has a smooth texture.	6.73	MA	5.57	SA	6.53	MA
2. has dense and substantial texture.	6.77	MA	5.70	SA	6.43	SA
3. has no residue texture.	6.40	SA	5.80	SA	6.77	MA
4. has a rich and indulgent texture	6.40	SA	5.13	FA	6.77	MA
5. has pleasurable and satisfying texture	6.33	SA	5.77	SA	6.50	MA
Overall Weighted Means	6.53	MA	5.59	SA	6.60	MA

It can be gleaned from the table that the group of Food Experts and Food Critics evaluated the GuyaSil Salad Dressing with 75 grams proportion as regard to texture as Moderately Acceptable with its overall weighted mean of 6.53 and 6.60, respectively, while Food Enthusiasts evaluated the product as Slightly Acceptable with its overall weighted mean of 5.59. These findings imply that the GuyaSil Salad Dressing has a smooth, dense and substantial, shows no residue, rich and indulgent, and has a pleasurable and satisfying texture.

Significant Differences in the Evaluation of the Three Groups of Respondents on the Level of Acceptability of Guyabano Pulp in Three Proportions with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing

As displayed in the table, the evaluations of the food experts, food enthusiasts and food critic respondents on the acceptability level of guyabano pulp in 55 grams proportion with basil leaves salad dressing in terms of appearance, aroma, color, taste and texture indicate significant differences. This leads to the conclusion that there are differences among the evaluations of the three groups of respondents.

Table 17. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 55 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Appearance	9.52	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
b. Aroma	4.38	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
c. Color	6.89	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
d. Taste	8.96	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
e. Texture	4.80	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant

Table 18. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 65 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Appearance	1.00	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
b. Aroma	4.59	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
c. Color	5.51	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
d. Taste	2.86	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
e. Texture	4.68	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant

It is noticeable in the table that the evaluations of the food experts, food enthusiasts and food critic respondents on the acceptability level of guyabano pulp in 65 grams proportion with basil leaves salad dressing in terms of aroma, color, and texture show significant differences with the computed F values which are above the critical F value. This means that the evaluations provided by the respondents vary except for appearance and taste.

Table 19. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 75 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Appearance	4.11	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
b. Aroma	4.81	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
c. Color	8.81	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
d. Taste	10.55	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
e. Texture	4.11	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant

Apparent from the table, the evaluations of the food experts, food enthusiasts and food critic respondents on the acceptability level of guyabano pulp in 75 grams proportion with basil leaves salad dressing in terms of appearance, aroma, color, taste and texture reveal significant differences with the respective computed F values which are greater than the critical F value. This shows that the respondents' evaluations given by the respondents exhibit variations.

Level of Marketability of Guyabano Pulp in Three Different Proportions with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing as perceived by the Three Groups of Respondents

For 55 Grams Proportion

Table 20. Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 55 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing in regard to Supply Availability

The GuyaSil salad dressing...	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. are available all year round.	3.93	VHP	3.67	VHP	3.07	HP
2. are locally available.	3.93	VHP	3.50	VHP	3.53	VHP
3. could be produced easily.	3.80	VHP	3.57	VHP	3.20	HP
Overall Weighted Means	3.89	VHP	3.58	VHP	3.27	HP

As gleaned from the table, the evaluation of the Food Experts and Food Enthusiasts on the GuyaSil Salad Dressing with 55 grams proportion in terms of Supply Availability obtained an overall weighted mean of 3.89, and 3.59, respectively which can be verbally interpreted as Very High Potential, while the evaluation of Food Critics obtained an overall weighted mean of 3.27, verbally interpreted as High Potential. The result implies that the respondents greatly agree that there is a sustainable and enough supply to produce the GuyaSil Salad Dressing.

This interpretation in table 21 was derived from the overall weighted mean of 4.00 for Food Experts, and 3.50 from Food Critics. Meanwhile, Food Enthusiasts rated the product as High Potential, evident from its overall weighted mean of 3.34. Overall, the data suggests that consumers are receptive to products that are both healthy and affordable.

Table 21. Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 55 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing in regard to Production Cost

The GuyaSil salad dressing...	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. is cheaper than other brands in the market.	4.00	VHP	3.40	HP	3.57	VHP
2. is economical.	4.00	VHP	3.33	HP	3.40	HP
3. can compete with the commercialized salad dressing.	4.00	VHP	3.30	HP	3.53	VHP
Overall Weighted Mean	4.00	VHP	3.34	HP	3.50	VHP

Table 22. Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 55 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing in regard to Consumer Demand

The GuyaSil salad dressing...	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. meet the demands of the consumers.	3.83	VHP	3.60	VHP	3.60	VHP
2. can give consumers health benefits.	3.83	VHP	3.50	VHP	3.53	VHP
3. can compete with other salad dressing that are available in the market.	3.93	VHP	3.50	VHP	3.50	VHP
Overall Weighted Mean	3.87	VHP	3.53	VHP	3.54	VHP

As shown in the table, Food Experts, Food Enthusiasts, and Food Critics evaluated the GuyaSil Salad Dressing in 55 grams proportion in terms of Consumer Demand as Very High Potential as seen from the overall weighted mean of 3.87, 3.53, and 3.54, consecutively. The data indicate that the product meet the demand of the consumers as it provides several health benefits and can definitely compete with other salad dressings in the market.

For 65 Grams Proportion

Table 23. Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 65 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing in regard to Supply Availability

The GuyaSil salad dressing...	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. are available all year round.	3.53	VHP	2.73	HP	3.00	HP
2. are locally available.	3.53	VHP	2.73	HP	3.30	HP
3. could be produced easily.	3.47	HP	2.73	HP	3.27	HP
Overall Weighted Means	3.51	VHP	2.73	HP	3.19	HP

It is perceptible from the table that in terms of supply availability, the Guyasil Salad Dressing in 65 grams proportion has Very High Potential as evaluated by the group of Food Experts with an overall weighted mean of 3.51, and has High Potential for Food Enthusiasts and Food Critics based from the overall weighted mean of 2.73 and 3.19. The result stems to the implication that the product can be consistently produced due to the abundant supplies available, while, simultaneously improving the ease of production from raw materials to the final product.

Table 24. Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 65 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing in regard to Production Cost

The GuyaSil salad dressing...	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. is cheaper than other brands in the market.	3.47	HP	3.13	HP	3.47	HP
2. is economical.	3.47	HP	3.07	HP	3.43	HP
3. can compete with the commercialized salad dressing.	3.47	HP	2.97	HP	3.27	HP
Overall Weighted Mean	3.47	HP	3.06	HP	3.39	HP

As described in the table, the evaluation of Food Experts, Food Enthusiasts, and Food Critics on the level of marketability of the GuyaSil Salad Dressing with 65 grams proportion in respect to Production Cost can be verbally interpreted as High Potential, with an overall weighted mean of 3.47, 3.06, and 3.39, respectively. The finding shows that the three groups of respondents all equally agree to the potential of the product in the market.

It can be depicted from the table 25 that Food Experts and Food Enthusiasts obtained an overall weighted mean of 3.34, and 2.79 which signifies that the GuyaSil Salad Dressing in 75 grams proportion has High Potential and has Very High Potential for Food Critics after obtaining an overall weighted mean of 3.51. This finding suggests that the consumer demand for the GuyaSil Salad Dressing in

65 grams proportion is highly probable in the market.

Table 25. Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 65 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing in regard to Consumer Demand

The GuyaSil salad dressing...	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. meet the demands of the consumers.	3.20	HP	2.80	HP	3.50	VHP
2. can give consumers health benefits.	3.37	HP	2.73	HP	3.60	VHP
3. can compete with other salad dressing that are available in the market.	3.47	HP	2.83	HP	3.43	HP
Overall Weighted Mean	3.34	HP	2.79	HP	3.51	VHP

For 75 Grams Proportion

Table 26. Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 75 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing in regard to Supply Availability

The GuyaSil salad dressing...	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. are available all year round.	3.53	VHP	2.83	HP	3.13	HP
2. are locally available.	3.53	VHP	2.83	HP	3.37	HP
3. could be produced easily.	3.47	HP	2.87	HP	3.17	HP
Overall Weighted Means	3.51	VHP	2.84	HP	3.22	HP

It can be gleaned from the table that Food Enthusiasts and Food Experts has similar evaluation on the GuyaSil Salad Dressing in 75 grams proportion as regards supply availability as seen from the overall weighted mean of 2.84 and 3.22 that can be verbally interpreted as High Potential, while the evaluation of Food Experts resulted to an overall weighted mean of 3.51, verbally interpreted as Very High Potential. This data implies that in terms of supply availability, the three groups of respondents all agree that the food raw materials required for the continuous production of the GuyaSil Salad Dressing are available all year round, locally available, and could be produced easily.

Table 27. Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 75 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing in regard to Production Cost

The GuyaSil salad dressing...	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. is cheaper than other brands in the market.	3.47	HP	3.17	HP	3.50	VHP
2. is economical.	3.47	HP	2.77	HP	3.40	HP
3. can compete with the commercialized salad dressing.	3.47	HP	2.83	HP	3.33	HP
Overall Weighted Mean	3.47	HP	2.92	HP	3.41	HP

Based on the table, the Food Experts, Food Enthusiasts, and Food Critics has similar evaluation on GuyaSil Salad Dressing in 75 grams proportion in regard to production cost, noticeable from its overall weighted mean of 3.47, 2.92, and 3.41, verbally interpreted as High Potential. The data imply that the products production cost is good and competitive compared to other commercialized brand, thus, can be more competitive once improvements supply purchasing has been made.

Table 28. Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 75 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing in regard to Consumer Demand

The GuyaSil salad dressing...	Respondents					
	Food Experts		Food Enthusiasts		Food Critics	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. meet the demands of the consumers.	3.20	HP	2.87	HP	3.50	VHP
2. can give consumers health benefits.	3.37	HP	2.77	HP	3.70	VHP
3. can compete with other salad dressing that are available in the market.	3.47	HP	2.60	HP	3.53	VHP
Overall Weighted Mean	3.34	HP	2.74	HP	3.58	VHP

As described from the table, with the overall weighted mean of 3.34 from Food Experts, and 2.74 from Food Enthusiasts, the Guyabano pulp in 75 grams with Basil leaves Salad dressing satisfies consumer demand as the overall weighted mean can be verbally interpreted as High Potential, while Food Critics gave an evaluation resulted to an overall weighted mean of 3.58, interpreted as Very High Potential. The results were good evidence that the product can provide health benefits and can compete among other salad dressings in the commercial market.

Significant Differences in the Perception of the Three Groups of Respondents on the Level of Marketability of Guyabano Pulp in Three Proportions with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing

Table 29. *Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 55 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing*

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Supply Availability	19.71	3.10	Reject the H_0	Significant
b. Production Cost	22.14	3.10	Reject the H_0	Significant
c. Consumer Demand	8.47	3.10	Reject the H_0	Significant

The table reflected that the perceptions of the food experts, food enthusiasts and food critic respondents on the marketability level of Guyabano pulp in 55 grams proportion with basil leaves salad dressing regarding supply availability, production cost, and consumer demand indicate significant differences with the respective computed F values which are above the critical F value. Thus, the perceptions of the respondents vary.

Table 30. *Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 65 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing*

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Supply Availability	17.11	3.10	Reject the H_0	Significant
b. Production Cost	6.77	3.10	Reject the H_0	Significant
c. Consumer Demand	20.07	3.10	Reject the H_0	Significant

Perusal to the table, the perceptions of the food experts, food enthusiasts and food critic respondents on the marketability level of guyabano pulp in 65 grams proportion with basil leaves salad dressing regarding supply availability, production cost, and consumer demand indicate significant differences with the respective computed F values which are more than the critical F value. This suggests that there exists variability in the perceptions of the respondents.

Table 31. *Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Perceptions on the Marketability Level of Guyabano Pulp in 75 Grams Proportion with Basil Leaves Salad Dressing*

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Supply Availability	8.82	3.10	Reject the H_0	Significant
b. Production Cost	6.72	3.10	Reject the H_0	Significant
c. Consumer Demand	22.82	3.10	Reject the H_0	Significant

As specified in the table, the perceptions of the food experts, food enthusiasts and food critic respondents on the marketability level of guyabano pulp in 75 grams proportion with basil leaves salad dressing regarding supply availability, production cost, and consumer demand indicate significant differences with the respective computed F values which are higher than the critical F value. Consequently, the perceptions of the survey groups of respondents vary.

Comments and Suggestions of the Three Groups of Respondents on the Concocted GuyaSil Salad Dressing for the Improvement of the Product

Comments

1. The GuyaSil Salad Dressing is considered most acceptable in the 55 grams proportion when compared to the proportions of 65 grams and 75 grams.
2. The GuyaSil Salad Dressing possesses a unique flavor and aroma reminiscent of guava.
3. The product offers great cost-effectiveness when compared to other salad dressings in the market.

Suggestions

1. Both the consistency and flavor of the GuyaSil Salad Dressing may still be enhanced.
2. Strive for a consistency that tends more towards a liquid nature.
3. The texture of the GuyaSil Salad Dressing with 75 grams proportion of Guyabano pulp may still be improved.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: GuyaSil Salad Dressing has low calorie content, high moisture content, sufficient acidity, low fat content qualifying for a "fat-free", minimal ash content indicating low inorganic compounds, and protein content within the appropriate range. Moreover, the physicochemical analysis of GuyaSil Salad Dressing complies with food standards, making it safe for consumption and a suitable recommendation for weight loss. The 55 grams, 65 grams, and 75 grams proportions were deemed acceptable by all three groups of respondents. Among these, the 55 grams proportion stood out

as the most acceptable concerning appearance, aroma, color, taste, and texture. The evaluations from the three respondent groups regarding GuyaSil Salad Dressing in three distinct proportions display noteworthy variations in terms of appearance, aroma, color, taste, and texture. The marketability level for GuyaSil Salad Dressing with 55 grams, 65 grams, and 75 grams proportions was promising. Additionally, among the three, the 55 grams proportion showed the most significant potential. As per the statistical results, there are significant differences in the respondents' evaluations of the product's marketability in terms of supply availability, production cost, and consumer demand. The GuyaSil Salad Dressing is both acceptable and marketable, with its unique fragrance and flavor playing a crucial role in consumer approval. Additionally, its pricing and convenience further contribute to its overall acceptability.

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